

Functional Outcome of Operative Technique of Acromioclavicular Joint Reconstruction using Double Endobutton

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Abstract:

The acromioclavicular (AC) joint function as a strut to help with movement of the scapula resulting in a greater degree of arm rotation. There are multiple modalities to treat AC joint disruption in patients. Both conservative and surgical management are possible and surgeon must choose the most appropriate management modality according to biological age, functional demand and type of lesion. This study aimed to evaluate the functional outcome of the double endobutton technique used to treat acromioclavicular (AC) dislocation. In this prospective study, 30 patients are treated for complete acromioclavicular (AC) joint disruption and their functional outcome are measured using Constant score and DASH score. Among 30 patients, 3 (10.00%) showed excellent functional outcome, 18 patients (60.00%) showed good outcome 8 patients (26.67%) showed fair outcome and only 1 patients (3.33%) showed poor functional outcome.

Keywords: Acromioclavicular Joint, Dislocation, Double Endobutton Technique, Surgery.

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Introduction

The acromioclavicular (ACJ) joint is the junction between the acromion and the clavicle. The acromioclavicular (ACJ) joint facilitates to raise the arm above the head. This joint function as a strut to help with movement of the scapula resulting in a greater degree of arm rotation. Acromioclavicular Joint (ACJ) dislocation is one of the earliest traumatic diseases [1] documented in the literature and accounts for 9% of all shoulder injuries [2]. Males between the ages of 20 and 39 are 10 times more likely it is most common in young people to develop it than females, and since it is linked to high-impact sports and high-speed road traffic car accidents.[3]

Acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocations are common shoulder girdle injuries in young, active people, accounting for up to half of all shoulder injuries among athletes, [5] particularly during contact sports like football, handball, and basketball. [6-8]The acromioclavicular (AC) ligaments, consisting of anterior, posterior, superior, and inferior ligaments, surround the acromioclavicular (AC) joint.

Among the capsular ligaments, fibers of the superior acromioclavicular (AC) ligament are the strongest, the deltoid and trapezius muscles blend with the fibers and are attached to the acromion process and the superior aspect of the clavicle. Stability of acromioclavicular (AC) joint is improved by muscle attachments. Horizontal plane

stability is given by these Ligaments. [9] Falling on an outstretched arm, locked in extension at the elbow, can lead the humeral head superior into the acromion typically resulting in low-grade acromioclavicular (AC) joint injuries.

A medial directed force to the lateral shoulder that drives the acromion into and underneath the distal clavicle, can result in higher degrees of injury and subsequently more displacement. [10]

There are multiple modalities to treat Acromioclavicle joint disruption in patients. Both conservative and surgical management are possible and surgeon must choose the most appropriate management modality according to biological age, functional demand and type of lesion. Here we are doing a study of treating AC joint disruption by various modalities and comparing its functional outcome.

Aims and Objectives:

- The functional outcome of treatment of acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation Type III to VI Rockwood and Green Classification by using double endobutton technique.
- To assess the reduction and acromioclavicular (AC) joint stability.
- To identify complications related with this procedure.

Objectives:- To evaluate the functional outcome of treatment of acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation by using double endobutton technique using DASH and Constant score and to evaluate the advantages of double endobutton technique over other modalities for treatment of acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation.

Methodology

It is a prospective observational study of 18 months of duration. Total 30 patients are taken for this study who is having acromioclavicular Joint (AC) dislocation (Rockwood type III-VI) patients treated by using the double endobutton technique.

Statistical analysis: The continuous variables were evaluated by mean (standard deviation) or range value when required. The dichotomous variables were presented in number/frequency and were analyzed using the Chi-square test. To compare the within group and between group variances amongst the study groups ANOVA test was used A p-value of <0.05 or 0.001 was regarded as significant.

Inclusion Criteria

- Complete acromioclavicular joint dislocation (Rockwood and Young type III-VI)
- Acute injuries
- Age group included are 18-60 years
- Closed injuries

Exclusion Criteria

- Chronic injuries
- Elderly patients (more than 60)
- Compound injuries
- Bleeding disorders
- Concomitant Clavicle fracture
- Infection at the operative site

Operative method:

All cases were operated on in our hospital Minimum of 9 months of post-operative follow-up. Outcome was measured based on the DASH questionnaire and constant score at intervals of 6 weeks, 12 weeks, 6 month and 9 month.

Radiological assessment is to be done at intervals of 6 weeks, 12 weeks, 6 month and 9 month. The Time protocol extends from within 24 hours of injury to 7 days of injury.

Procedure and Postoperative Protocol:

General measures: All patients who received an emergency were evaluated for any associated major injuries like chest and brachial plexus injuries. Patient was immobilized with an arm sling. Then x-ray of the involved shoulder AP, Zanca viewed an x-ray of both shoulders standing STRESS AP view was taken. [4]

Preoperative assessment and preparation: All the patients were explained about the surgery and appropriate and valid written consent were taken. The patient was taken for surgery after routine investigation and after obtaining fitness towards surgery. All pre-operative investigations are performed. A dose of tetanus toxoid and antibiotic were given pre-operatively.

Surgical technique: After pre-anaesthetic check-up and optimization, patient taken to operative table in supine position with sandbag under scapular blade for visualization of coracoid anatomy. A 2 inch incision was made from the palpable base of the coracoid tip to the anterior edge of the distal clavicle. Medial and lateral skin flaps were developed. The deltoid splitted in line with its fibers, and the coracoid was identified and cleared off all the way to the base. The medial and lateral edges of the coracoid at the base are clearly identified.

The clavicle was manually reduced, and while the reduction was being held, a drill tip guide wire was drilled into the top of the clavicle approximately 3 cm medial to the acromioclavicular (AC) joint and midway between the anterior and posterior border of the clavicle. The drill hole should be directly over the base of the coracoid, and the drill should be aimed slightly anteriorly. After drilling through the clavicle, the guide wire was easily visualized in between the clavicle and coracoid. Once the tip of the guide wire was confirmed to be entering the coracoid well centered between the medial and lateral edges, it is then drilled all the way throughout the base.

The 4.5-mm endobutton drill now was used to ream over the drill tip guide wire. With the clavicle well reduced, the endobutton depth gauge was used to determine the channel length. A second 2.5-mm drill hole was placed 1 cm lateral to the endobutton drill hole. The appropriate size endobutton closed loop (CL) was choosen, and 2 number 5 ethibond sutures were placed through the first and fourth holes of the endobutton. A third suture was placed at the apex of the loop of the endobutton CL.

This suture was well marked so it could be identified as the loop stitch. Using a 3.2-mm smooth cylindrical plunger, the endobutton, along with its associated sutures, was pushed into the top of the clavicle through the previously drilled hole. The endobutton was visualized in the space between clavicle and coracoid and then pushed further going into the coracoid drill hole until it “popped” out the underside of the coracoid. The loop stitch was pulled up, locking the endobutton onto the underside of the coracoid. One of the 2 pairs of suture tails was pulled out of the interval between the coracoid and clavicle. This left 1 suture (2 tails) going from the coracoid endobutton

exiting the top of the clavicle. With firm downward pressure on the clavicle to maintain maximum reduction, the loop stitch is pulled up. With very firm upward pull on the loop stitch, the very tip of the endobutton CL loop was seen to be protruding from the top of the clavicular hole.

A free endobutton was held with a suture holder and slid into the protruding loop so that it was placed centered under the loop. It is extremely important that the endobutton be held on its edge, not lying flat against the bone. Passed the suture tails exiting the top of the clavicle through endobutton holes (it is best to use holes 2 and 3) on either side of the endobutton CL loop. With the suture holder, now turned the endobutton so it layed flat on bone. Tied the sutures on top of the endobutton Closed loop (CL).

This now locks the loop in place and completes the reconstruction of the conoid portion of the coracoclavicular ligament. Retrieve the suture tails that were brought out of the coracoclavicular space and pass 1 tail through the second (2.5-mm) drill hole. Tied the suture. This recreates the trapezoid portion of the coracoclavicular ligament.

Post-Operative Protocol:

Pendulum exercises were started on the 2nd post-operative day, and passive mobilization started as patient tolerated. Within 3 weeks, active exercises were started, and the full range of movements starts after 3 weeks.

Outcome measures of treatment of acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation by using double endobutton technique

1. Constant Score
2. Dash Score

We used the DASH questionnaire, Constant score as they reflect the subjective and objective perspective of the shoulder function. The range of movements required in the Constant score were measured with a goniometer. The DASH score ranges from 0-100, where zero is the best score and indicates excellent results. Similarly score of 100 indicates a poor result. For the constant score, a top score of 100 indicates the highest and excellent results, while zero indicates the least score and poor result. At each visit, the patients were evaluated for signs of implant failure, irritation, impingement or infection. Radiographs were taken preoperative, immediately postoperative and subsequently at 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months and 9 months. Placement of the endobutton, reduction of acromioclavicular (AC) joint and CC calcification were assessed at serial intervals.

Results

Constant score:- At 6 weeks, maximum 12(40.00%) of the patients had 0-55 constant score while only 3(10.00%) had 86-100. However, at 9 months, the maximum of 17(56.67%) had score of 86-100. At each follow-up, the constant score gradually increased and the differences was statistically significant [p=0.0018]. (Fig.1)

Figure 1: Constant Score

DASH score:- At 6 weeks, maximum 10(33.33%) of the patients had 86-100 dash score while only 6(20.00%) had 0-55. However, at 9 months, the maximum of 18(60.00%) patients had score of 0-55. At each follow-up, the DASH score gradually decreased and the differences were significant [p=0.0069]. (Fig 2)

Figure 2: Dash Score

Post-operative complications: - Only 6 out of 30 patients suffered complication such as Stitch granuloma, superficial infection, Shoulder stiffness,

Pain and Redislocation of acromioclavicular (AC) joint. Statistically complications were significant among enroll patients [p=0.9124]. (Fig 3)

Figure 3: Complications

Functional outcome:- Among 30 patients enroll in this study 3 (10.00%) showed excellent functional outcome, 18 patients (60.00%) showed good

outcome 8 patients (26.67%) showed fair outcome and only 1 patients (3.33%) showed poor functional outcome. (Table 1)

Table 1: Functional outcome

Functional Outcome	N	%	P-Value
Excellent	3	10.00%	X=34.43 P<0.0001*
Good	18	60.00%	
Fair	8	26.67%	
Poor	1	3.33%	

Discussion

The study aimed to evaluate the functional outcome of the double endobutton technique used to treat acromioclavicular (AC) dislocation. In this prospective study, 30 patients with complete acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation were enrolled. 70.00% of the patients were 20-39 years old. Male preponderance was observed (66.67%), and most patients belonged to the lower middle class (33.33%). However, most of the socio-demographic parameters were non-significant. Most patients had an injury on the right side (70.00%), and the commonest mode of injury was road traffic accidents (66.67%) which was significant. Nordin J et al. [11] reported that sports injuries were the most prevalent cause of injury (42%), followed by RTA (34%), falls (20%), and other causes (3%). Likewise, in the previous study, Chillemi et al. [12] found that sports injury was the most common form of injury (70%) and that vehicle accidents were the second most common cause of dislocation. The majority of the patients were under the type III grading (33.33%). Sureshkumar A et al. [9] found that type V was the most prevalent injury, occurring in 45% of patients, followed by 30% of cases with type IV injuries. Numerous studies have shown that the appropriate treatment for acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation varies depending on the severity of the injury and the involvement of soft tissues. It is well established for all categories except type III, which remains debatable. Among all the patients, 43.33% had surgery within 5 days of trauma. 43.33% of the patients had 40-60 minutes of duration of surgery. Most patients (50.00%) had 100-150 ml of blood loss. At 6 weeks, maximum 12 (40.00%) of the patients had 0-55 constant score while only 3 (10.00%) had 86-100. However, at 9 months, the maximum of 17 (56.67%) had score of 86-100. At each follow-up, the constant score gradually increased and the differences was statistically significant [$p=0.0018^*$]. Post operatively radiographs are taken and ROM checked at all stages (Fig 4). At 6 weeks, maximum 10 (33.33%) of the patients had 86-100 DASH score while only 6 (20.00%) had 0-55. However, at 9 months, the maximum of 18 (60.00%) patients had score of 0-55. At each follow-up, the DASH score gradually decreased and the differences were significant [$p=0.0069^*$]. Beris A et al. [13] reported that the mean DASH score reduced dramatically from 19.6 (14-28; poor score) to 0.25 (excellent score) from pre-operative levels at the last follow-up. Only 6 out of 100 patients suffered complication such as Stitch granuloma, superficial infection, shoulder stiffness, pain and re-dislocation of AC joint. Statistically complications were non-significant among enroll patients [$p=0.9124$]. Based on the findings of this study, it has been observed that the younger age group and male gender were at higher

risk. Acromioclavicular (AC) joint reconstruction by endobutton results in early functional recovery and a full range of shoulder movements. However, to validate this method, a protocol for treatment of acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation, bigger sample size and more prolonged follow-up is required.

Conclusion

The treatment of acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocation by using double endobutton technique is minimally invasive procedure which maintains the biomechanism of acromioclavicular (AC) joint. The endobutton loop provides good strength and stability to acromioclavicular (AC) joint. The endobutton loop simulates the function of CC ligament. Advantages of double endobutton technique over other modalities of treatment of AC joint dislocation are good anatomical reduction, minimally invasive procedure, smaller scar, less blood loss and shorter duration of surgery. The double endobutton technique also have least complications such as brachial plexus injury, high volume blood loss post-operative complications such as wound infection, shoulder stiffness and post-operative pain are least. As well as early post-operative rehabilitations included pendulum exercises started on second post-operative day and passive mobilization started as patient tolerated. Within 3 weeks active exercises were started and full range of movement started after 3 weeks.

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